

STUDY TITLE: Mapping the Emergency Medicine Landscape in Tanzania: A Workforce and Health Facility Study Fifteen Years After Its Introduction

Appendix 2: Data Collection Tool : Facility Data Tool

- 1) Name of Facility (mention)
- 2) Type of Facility
 - a. Public
 - b. Private
 - c. Faith based organization/NGO
- 3) Facility Level
 - a. Dispensary
 - b. Health Center
 - c. District Hospital
 - d. Regional Referral Hospital
 - e. Zonal Hospital/ Hospital at Zonal Level
 - f. National Specialized Hospital
 - g. National Hospital
- 4) District Present (mention)
- 5) Region present (mention)
- 6) Rural/Urban Classification
 - a. Rural
 - b. Urban
- 7) Department establishment year (mention)
- 8) Number of emergency physicians present
- 9) Population served / catchment area